

Effectiveness of Internal Audit functions under the framework of International Standards of Internal Auditing in public sector universities of Pakistan.

Zahid Qadeer*

Ph.d Scholar, IBS, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Pakistan

zahidqadeer@kust.edu.pk

Dr. Sammar Abbas

Associate Professor, IBS, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Pakistan

Sabbas@kust.edu.pk

Dr. Tanveer Ahmad

Lecturer, IBS, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Pakistan

Tanveerahmad@kust.edu.pk

Abstract

This paper provides empirical evidence that complying with the International Standards of Internal Auditing (ISIA) is helpful for Effectiveness of Internal Audit (EIA) in public sector universities of Pakistan having Audit Committee (AC) as moderating variable. Research site for this study is 50 public sector universities of our interest across Pakistan wherein the mandatory function of internal audit function exists. Questionnaire is adapted in the light of existing literature on a 5-point likert scale. Data is collected from 150 personnel of finance/audit departments and members of statutory bodies. AMOS is used for testing of instrument' reliability and validity. Data was analyzed for fulfillment of assumptions of regression. The regression results indicates significant positive association between ISIA and EIA. The overall model found significant with $F = 66.370$ having $R^2 = 0.475$, $p < 0.001$. This implies that those public sector institutes where the compliance level of international standards is higher have more dynamic role of internal audit. Moderating analysis shows that there is significant moderating effect of AC between the relationship of ISIA and EIA. Findings are useful in strengthening the internal audit in public sector of Pakistan. Policy makers are recommended for adoption of international standards of internal auditing alongwith the establishment of Audit Committee (AC) as a supervisory body which may lead to enhanced effectiveness of internal audit (EIA) function in public sector universities of Pakistan. However, results cannot be generalized for corporate sector. Future studies may be conducted in the private sector perspective for more insight.

Key words

Internal Auditing, International Standards, Public Sector, Audit Committee.

Introduction

Internal auditing is described as “an independent, objective assurance & consulting activity designed to add value & improve an organization's operations, helps an organization accomplish its objectives by bringing a systematic, disciplined approach to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control, and governance processes” by the institute of Internal Auditor., (IIA, 1999). The growing importance of Internal Audit function is demonstrated by the emerging demand for this profession in all government and private organisations (Cohen & Sayag 2010). Over the years, the value of internal audit has been elevated in the market scenario due to its service

achievements and contributions (Dellai & Omri 2016). The Internal Audit Institute (IIA) has created internal auditing standards exclusively to provide guidance and to provide the conceptual framework for carrying out and developing internal auditing operations in light of the development of internal audit as a profession. These standards extended to two main groups, namely; (i) attribute standards and (ii) performance standards. Performance Standards narrates the purpose of internal auditing and provide standards of excellence by which the utility of these services may be evaluated. While Attribute Standards covers the characteristics of organizations and persons undertaking internal auditing.

The Auditing and Accounting scandals have shown the importance of applying stricter rules of corporate governance, accounting, and auditing. An effective internal control system in public sector organizations by complying with the international standards is much necessary for both strong and weak financial systems (Kaya & Utku, 2021). Necessary guidance about the Standards is provided by the International Institute of Internal Auditing (IIA) in the Practice consultancies and advisories and are recommended, nevertheless, not mandatory for entire internal auditors (Marais et al., 2009).

The consequences of the international financial crisis motivated legislators to be more attentive towards non-commercial and non-profit organizations to focus more on adherence with the appropriate practices and this paradigm shift has considerably improved awareness on risk management and organizational governance (Pelser et al., 2020). Having good working relationship and coordination with internal auditors lead to preventing unwanted duplication of work by external auditors that add values in exchanging materials, debating audit reports and facilitating higher-quality audits for information sharing (Alqudah et al., 2019).

In both public and commercial businesses, internal auditing function (IAF) has evolved into a crucial control tool. Internal auditing functions have historically been created to assist assure accurate accounting information and to protect organization from any potential risk (Mexmonov 2020). Owing to the reason of diversified cultural, legal, and economic variations influence in various countries, the practice of internal audit standards do provide a unifying method for boosting value and consistency across organizations.. (IIA 2007). Public sector organizations are founded under some legal framework having a status of complete or semi-autonomy with the aim to, provide services or goods to general public on a subsidize, partial or self-financing basis while sometimes state contribute towards its share through budgetary support (Alexopoulos et al., 2023).

To oversee the activities of internal auditing within organization, Audit Committees (AC) has been recognized and created as a monitoring body through numerous governance modifications which made up of experienced members in the relevant professions. (Vera-Munoz, 2005). These Committees are primarily made up of independent directors who have sufficient financial and accounting knowledge and are unaffected by the management's influence. (Rashid et al., 2021). The oversight role of financial reporting is supposed to be carried out by the Audit Committees established within the governance framework (Setiany et al., 2017).

- To determine the impact of international attribute standards of internal auditing (IAS)

on the effectiveness of internal audit (EIA) functions in public sector universities in Pakistan.

- To determine the impact of international performance standards of internal auditing (IPS) on the effectiveness of internal audit (EIA) functions in public sector universities in Pakistan.
- To evaluate the moderating impact of audit committee (AC) on the relationship between predictor[s] and outcome variable[s].

The mandatory role of internal audit is supported by legislation in around 50 public sector universities across Pakistan which is identified through respective provincial assemblies' act/ordinance in each province. This is also evident from the model universities act 2012 of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province and recently promulgated Balochistan universities model act 2022. While in rest of the provinces, the position of internal audit vary from university to university due to a separate and dedicated act/ordinance for each university. Moreover, the position of internal auditors is still relatively new in public universities of Pakistan as compare to traditional role of resident auditors who are deputed by the government from outside the organization. There is very limited work on International internal auditing standards (IIAS) in Pakistan. Even though internal auditing is now practicing in Pakistan's public universities, the compliance with international standards is still very lax in these institutions. This study will assess compliance levels at national level and will provide recommendations on how to improve the efficiency of internal audit in Pakistan's public universities. Internal auditing is now becoming more prevalent among various public sector and government officials as a result of their growing awareness of its significance.

Literature review

International Standards of internal auditing

The international standards of internal auditing clarifies while drawing up a risk-based plan of audit engagements within organization requires coordination from senior management and the board (or the audit committee), but that the plan should be based independent judgement of an auditor (Chambers 2014). Leung & Cooper (2009) mentioned that respondents selected from east Asian counties. All report of using Standards at a moderately high degree. However, the majority of responders that claim to be in complete compliance with the Standards are from Australia. Priscilla et al. (2009) demonstrates the variations in use and adherence to the Standards by respondents' IAAs between Europe and the USA. There is a substantial amount of regional variance in the responses. IIA's Standards and certifications are the same for all countries, the growth of the internal auditing profession has been influenced by new national legislation, stock exchange requirements, and corporate governance standard. (Burnaby et al., 2009). So we formulate following hypothesis:

H1: The International Attribute Standards of Internal Auditing significantly impact the effectiveness of internal audit in public sector universities of Pakistan.

- H2: The International Performance Standards of Internal Auditing significantly impact the effectiveness of internal audit in public sector universities of Pakistan.

Internal Audit Effectiveness

The measurement of effectiveness of internal audit (EIA) is based on six determinants which include reporting, management support, internal control, regulatory requirement, liaison with external audit and risk management. Soh & Bennie (2011) examined internal auditing (IA) current performance evaluation procedures. The results imply that IA performance evaluation systems have not advanced simultaneously and found that the role of IA and its efficacy significantly be refocused and broadened. Ganesan et. al., (2017) conducted study in 120 manufacturing industries listed in Malaysia and explained how the internal audit function (IAF) has a moderating effect on the traits of audit committee. Tahir et. al., (2019) make an effort to found that better management support and internal auditor competencies have a favorable impact on internal audit effectiveness. Singh et. al., (2021) analyzes 12 multinational firms in Malaysia using structural equation modeling. The results show that interdepartmental coordination, management assistance, and auditee acceptance and support were all factors in internal audit effectiveness.

Audit Committee

The measurement of latin variable (AC) comprise of five factors which are independence, size of committee, frequency of meeting, tenure, experience. Zaman & Sarens (2013) aims to uncovers proof that the informal contacts between audit committee members are significantly and favorably related to the independence of the committee, the expertise and experience of the audit chair, and the caliber of internal audits. Aryan (2015) displayed keen interest to highlight the function of external audit and the audit committee in raising business profitability Jordan's industrial sector. Multiple regression analysis discovered that there were significant positive correlations between audit committee meetings, audit committee size, and company profitability, but no correlations between audit committee composition, member literacy, or audit quality and profitability. He et. al., (2017) analyze the impact of the auditors' and audit committee members' interpersonal relationships on the audit results. There is evidence that the social connections between engagement auditors and audit committee members affect the quality of the audit. Alzeban (2015) explore to offer empirical support for the relationship between audit committee traits and compliance with the International Standards for the Professional Practice of Internal Auditing (ISPPA) for internal audit in Saudi corporations listed on the Saudi Stock. The findings show that the audit committee's features affect internal audit compliance with the ISPPA. This discussion leads to form following hypothesis:

- H3a: Audit committee significantly moderate the relationship between International Attributes Standards of International Auditing with overall effectiveness of internal audit in public sector universities of Pakistan.
- H3b: Audit committee significantly moderate the relationship between International Performance Standards of International Auditing with overall effectiveness of internal audit in public sector universities of Pakistan.

Conceptual Framework

This study is comprise of 4 latent variables which are measured with 41 items through operationalization technique. This model was built based on combination of different frameworks e.g. The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), 2017, Alzeban (2015), Rashid et al. (2021), Nipper 2021), Shakeel et al. (2020), Christopher (2015), Kaya, & Utku, (2021), Pelser et al., (2020), Wallace, (2004), Asare, (2009).

Methodology

This study is undertaken in public sector universities across different provinces of Pakistan wherein regulatory internal audit function exists. Research site for this study is 50 public sector universities of our interest wherein the mandatory function of internal audit function exists by virtue of legislation. A questionnaire is adapted in the light of existing literature on a 5-point likert scale and distributed amongst 200 personnel of finance & audit sections alongwith members of statutory bodies using google form as well as in person. 150 (75%) filled questionnaire are received. Face validity and content validity is checked through experts. Composite reliability (CR), convergent and discriminant validity of the instrument is tested using AMOS 26.0. It is then analyzed for fulfillment of assumptions of regression e.g normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation and heteroscedacity using SPSS Statistics 22.0.

Descriptive Analysis

Data collected from 3 different groups within public sector universities as per given detail:

S#	Groups	Frequency	Percent
1	Finance Section	99	66
2	Internal Audit Sectors	33	22
3	Statutory bodies Members	18	12

Total	150	100
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The data collected from universities are different in terms of their age:

S#	Established	Frequency	Percent
1	5 Years ago	40	26.7
2	10 Years ago	33	22.0
3	15 Years ago	22	14.7
4	20 or more Years ago	55	36.7
	Total	150	100.0

Test of Assumptions for Regression Analysis

Normality Test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests are employed to ascertain normality in the data. Moreover a histogram is created to visualize the distribution of data to observe a perfect bell curve.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Audit Committee	.099	150	.015	.987	150	.193
Effectiveness of Internal Audit (EIA)	.042	150	.200*	.992	150	.537
Attribute Standards	.062	150	.200*	.991	150	.445
Performance Standards	.067	150	.095	.980	150	.029

The test was performed in SPSS 22.0 and results shows that P-value > 0.05 all variables are bell-shaped hence we conclude that the data for all variables is normality distributed.

Multicollinearity

It typically happens when two or more predictor variables have substantial correlations with one another. The regression estimations may be unstable and unreliable when Multicollinearity is present.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.492	.165		2.983	.003		
	Attribute Standards	.308	.103	.258	2.977	.003	.476	2.102
	Performance Standards	.544	.099	.479	5.522	<.001	.476	2.102

Dependent Variable: EIA

As the value of VIF is less than 10 hence no multicollinearity exists in data

Heteroscedasticity test

It is a situation when the distribution of the residuals undergoes a systematic change throughout the range of measured values which makes heteroscedasticity problem.

Breusch-Pagan test

We generate residuals and then take square of residuals. Thereafter we regress Square of residuals with independent variables. Here are results

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.607	2	.304	.636	.531 ^b
	Residual	70.222	147	.478		
	Total	70.830	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Square.Residuals

b. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Standards, Attribute Standards

P-value > 0.05 hence we accept conclude that that there is no heteroscedasticity in the data.

Autocorrelation:

The degree of similarity between a given time series and its lag-version over subsequent time periods is measured by autocorrelation.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. Change	F Durbin-Watson
				Square Change	F	df1	df2		
1	.689 ^a	.475	.523	.475	66.370	2	147	<.001	2.11

a. Predictors: (Constant), PerformanceStandards, Attribute_Standards

b. Dependent Variable: EIA

Here the value of Darban Watson is between 1.5 > 2.5 then its acceptable that the data do not have the problem of autocorrelation.

Reliability

The qualities of the measurements used in the study should be evaluated to develop confidence in their effectiveness and ensure minimal measurement error. (Field, 2009). Initially we carried out reliability analysis for each item for the measurement of four constructs separately e.g Attribute Standards of internal auditing = 0.733, Performance Standards of internal auditing= 0.859, Audit Committee=0.903 and Effectiveness of Internal Audit = 0.875. Overall Cronbach Alpha at 0.845.

Validity

Convergent Validity

The level of correlation between the items that theoretically make up a single construct is measured by convergent validity.

S#	Variables	Item Name	Factor Loading	Composite Reliability	AVE
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1	International Attribute Standards of Internal Audit (IAS)	IAS-1	0.69	0.733	0.702
2		IAS-2	0.67		
3		IAS-3	0.89		
4		IAS-4	0.61		
5		IAS-5	0.69		
6		IAS-6	0.75		
7		IAS-7	0.81		
8		IAS-8	0.75		
9		IAS-9	0.85		
1	International Performance Standards of Internal Audit (IPS)	IPS-1	0.65	0.859	0.648
2		IPS-2	0.59		
3		IPS-3	0.65		
4		IPS-4	0.86		
5		IPS-5	0.56		
6		IPS-6	0.75		
7		IPS-7	0.66		
8		IPS-8	0.63		
9		IPS-9	0.76		
10		IPS-10	0.74		
11		IPS-11	0.85		
12		IPS-12	0.9		
1	Audit Committee (AC)	AC-1	0.54	0.903	0.575
2		AC-2	0.66		
3		AC-3	0.67		
4		AC-4	0.82		
5		AC-5	0.7		
6		AC-6	0.64		
7		AC-7	0.82		
8		AC-8	0.8		
9		AC-9	0.88		
10		AC-10	0.86		

1	Effectiveness of Internal Auditing (EIA)	EIA-1	0.62	0.875	0.620
2		EIA-2	0.89		
3		EIA-3	0.68		
4		EIA-4	0.74		
5		EIA-5	0.72		
6		EIA-6	0.69		
7		EIA-7	0.69		
8		EIA-8	0.6		
9		EIA-9	0.58		
10		EIA-10	0.53		
11		EIA-11	0.69		

CFA results depicts that model has good fit statistics e.g. CMIN/df=2.889, RMSEA of 0.113, RMR of 0.217 & CFI of 0.904. These recommended values are given in the bracket based on the guidelines of Hu & Bentler (1999) and Browne & Cudeck (1992) (RMSEA<.113, RMR<.217, CFI>.904). All these given items are standardized factor loading and are above 0.50 while AVE is also above 0.50 so it is an indication of good convergent validity (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Gudergan, 2017). The composite reliability (CR) for all variables are above 0.70 so it shows that our variables had good reliability as well.

Discriminant Validity

A scale's discriminant validity is determined by how well its items or measures don't correspond to other constructs. (Hariri & Roberts 2015).

	IAS	IPS	A.C	EIA
IAS	0.702	0.624	0.475	0.600
IPS	0.624	0.648	0.564	0.605
A.C	0.475	0.564	0.575	0.526
EIA	0.605	0.605	0.526	0.620

For verifying the discriminant validity, Fornell & Larcker (1981) criteria I employed. These values in the diagonal bold are square root of AVE while other values are for inter-variable correlation. The mandatory requirement is that the diagonal bold values must be higher than other values in all its respective columns and rows which is met here and can

be viewed in the table. Hence, we can conclude that our variables in the model have good discriminant validity.

Results and discussion

Regression Analysis

One of the current study’s objective is to determine the effect of International Standards of internal audit on the effectiveness of internal audit (EIA) in public sector universities of Pakistan, which also includes the Audit Committee as a moderator. The type of association between the independent and dependent variables may vary when the model includes a moderation effect (Hair et al., 2014). In this way, the structural model is first conducted without the moderator, and after that, the moderation can be reliably tested and examined in an another model (Hair et al., 2014). So this study has two separate models – the direct effects model and the interaction effects model.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.492	.165		2.983	.003		
1 Performance Standards	.544	.099	.479	5.522	.000	.476	2.102
Attribute Standards	.308	.103	.258	2.977	.003	.476	2.102

Model Summary^b

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error Change Statistics		F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F Durbin-Watson	
			Estimate	of the R Square						
1	.689 ^a	.475	.467	.523	.475	66.370	2	147	.000	2.11

a. Predictors: (Constant), Attribute_Standards, Performance Standards

b. Dependent Variable: EIA

In this regression results, the overall model is significant at $p < .05$, with an adjusted R² of .467 which implies that 46.7% variation in Effectiveness of Internal Audit (EIA) in public sector universities of Pakistan is explained by International Standards of internal auditing. Coefficients of the independent variables (International Attribute Standards of internal audit $p < .05$ and International Performance Standards of internal audit $p < .05$) are significant. Which shows a significant positive association (supporting H₁ and H₂) suggesting that the compliance of international standards of internal auditing is associated with greater effectiveness of internal auditing in public sector universities.

Moderating analysis

We have used indirect method to calculate moderating effect in the relationship. We have run the regression after centering the predictor because not doing it β coefficient represent that effect when other predictor are zero which is very rare in real world. Hence centering the predictor value will give us the results having actual value of other predictors.

Model		Beta	t	Sig	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		4.057	.000		
	Performance Standards	.419	4.527	.000	.393	2.545
	Attribute Standards	.205	2.392	.018	.458	2.183
	Audit committee	.219	3.062	.003	.659	1.98
	Int_ AttrSTND x AC	.193	2.016	.046	.368	2.718
	Int_ PerfSTND x AC	.199	2.051	.042	.355	2.816

Interaction terms of moderator and independent variables were analyzed to check the moderating effect and its hypotheses. P value is < 0.05 means we infer that there is moderating effect between dependent variables and independent variables. It means Audit Committee (AC) moderate the relationship between International Attribute Standards of Internal Auditing (IAS) and International Performance Standards of Internal Auditing (IPS).

Discussion and Future Directions

The objective of this study was to analyze and understand the influence of the International Standards of Internal Auditing on the overall effectiveness of the internal audit in public sector universities of Pakistan. A framework was developed in the light of existing literature to measure latent variables to evaluate the overall IAF effectiveness. The results indicate that compliance with the international standards with the internal auditing is positively associated with the IAF effectiveness which are consistent with Kaya, Y., & Utku, M. (2021). Audit Committee is used as a moderator to see whether its existence in public sector setup influence the relationship between International standards of internal audit upon the effectiveness of internal auditing. These Audit committee (AC) exists in public sector universities and its moderating effect analysis reveals that there is a significant interaction effect on the relationship of international standards of internal auditing and Effectiveness of internal auditing which are in line with the prior study by (Alzeban (2015; Rashid et al., 2021).. Future research may be conducted to explore other factors which influence on Effectiveness of internal audit. Moreover the results of this study can't be generalized to corporate sector due to entirely different paradigm.

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